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Upgraded RI Report

SALTOpower

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D2.2: Upgraded RI Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Aiming at reporting the design, installation and commissioning state of the Widening RI upgrade developed along SALTOpower JRA, this report includes not only information pertaining to the activities in Task 2.3 aiming at the upgrade of the Widening RI, including:

- layout schemes for installation of inlet/outlet for Molten Salt connections in HPS2 and NEWSOL loops;
- inlet/outlet operation parameters (mass flow, temperatures, pressure, etc.);
- list of materials/services (engineering, piping, valves, sensors, etc.),

but also the implementation of distributed facility features enabling the remote access and crossed services among the RIs of SALTOpower Consortium partners, namely:

- remote monitoring: RI assets list (all RIs); system architecture; implementation scheme (assets, existing sensors, additional sensors, cabling, wireless communication, etc.);
- definition of common front-end;
- definition of data access rules, and implementation of data storage framework;
- description of implementation/functionality.

Despite delays with e.g. procurement and delivery of components or approval of external access to some of TOP partners' RI, impairing the full commissioning of the Widening RI upgrade and full fledged remote infrastructure, the activities completed secure its ensuing completion, and this report provides a concrete roadmap and calendar for the completion of the missing tasks to full commissioning.

2. WIDENING RI UPGRADE

In view of enabling a widened scope of services (e.g. scale wise) but also of the ensuing demonstration activities following the “energy hub” concept developed in SALTOpower “beyond state-of-the-art” concept (see Deliverable 2.1), the activities pertaining the upgrade of the pre-existing research infrastructure (RI) at the Widening partner included the design, construction and commissioning of heat and power interfaces enabling the ensuing coupling of additional system components (e.g. high-temperature electrolyser for the ensuing production of H₂; shell-and-tube pyrolysis reactor for the ensuing generation of syngas from different biomass samples).

Following a philosophy of optimization of ensuing services and/or activities, the definition of the Widening RI upgrade evolved from its initial concept, around a fixed downstream input set on an electrolyser “test bed”, to a more flexible (and robust) approach maximizing not only the potential list of services and component couplings possible, but also the scale of experiments and the full fledged use of both molten salt loops existing in the RI.

2.1 RI upgrade design and layout

To the upgrade of the Widening RI, two new pairs of inlet/outlet plugs (I/O plug) to the MS loop have been defined, one in each of the MS loops: HPS2 loop, including a MS driven solar field and a 2-tank MS TES, and NEWSOL loop, including a thermocline MS TES, as illustrated in Figure 2.1.

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.1: View of the Widening RI pre-existing MS loops (a) HPS2 and (b) NEWSOL

Each I/O plug consists of regulating (and shut-off) valves, inlet and outlet temperature sensors and mass flow measurement, enabling a due monitoring and control of the molten salt mass flow provided to the coupled component or system.

Furthermore, circulation in the MS loop enables each of the I/O plugs to be operated in a charging (i.e. supplying hot MS at the plug inlet, receiving cold MS at the plug outlet) or discharging (i.e. supplying cold MS at the plug inlet, receiving hot MS at the plug outlet) modes.

A layout scheme of the pre-existing MS loops and of the SALTOpower I/O plug upgrade is presented in Figures 2.2 and 2.3 for HPS2 and NEWSOL loops, respectively.

The operation parameters enabled in each of the I/O plugs are summarized in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: SALTOpower I/O plug operation parameters

Parameters of the inlets	HPS2-Loop	Newsol Loop
Mass flow	0.2-2kg/s	0.02-0.2kg/s
Inlet temperature	Tmin 290°C - Tmax 550 °C	Tmin 190°C, Tmax 500°C
Outlet temperature	Tmin 290°C - Tmax 580 °C	Tmin 190°C, Tmax 520°C
Available thermal power	0.1 - 1 MW.th	10 - 100 kW.th
Available cooling power	1.8 MW.th	500 kW.th
Cooling type	Water, steam generator (under maintenance, to be commissioned in Q3'26).	Air, natural convection (forced convection to be commissioned June'26)
Composition of MS %	60%NaNO ₃ 40%KNO ₃	42% CaNO ₃ , 43% KNO ₃ , 15% NaNO ₃

2.2 Current status of installation and commissioning

The list of materials and works to be procured is summarised in Table 2.2 with the specification of the materials chosen and the current status of installation. Until the end of October'25 it was possible to receive piping material, temperature sensors, flowmeter and contract welding and insulation works. On the other hand, it was not possible to receive either the control and shut off valves, which impacted the installation of the remaining instrumentation (flow and temperature meters), welding, heat tracing, insulation works, and to finally commissioning the new inlets/outlets.

The delays in delivery of these valves are related to delays with the procurement process inside the university, and details of the controllers that were only fixed after several technical validations between the supplier and UEV to customize the valves to the desired mass flows. The estimated delivery time of the valves was communicated to be by the end of December, according to information given by the supplier.

Currently, it is expected that it should be possible to do the installation and commissioning of this inlet in Q2 of 2026 and in accordance with Table 2.3. The completion of the pending works is secured, in whatever expenditures falling outside the SALTOpower eligible costs period, by UEVORA's own funding.

Table 2.2.: Designation and description of materials and services procured to HPS2 and NEWSOL loops

Designation	HPS2	NEWSOL	Status
Piping material and welding works	ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP321H Dims to ASME B36.10	ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP304H Dims to ASME B36.10	delivered
Control valves	SS body with controller, mass flow 02-2kg/s	SS body with controller mass flow 0,02-0,2kg/s	to be delivered until December '25
Manual shut off valves	3", ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP304H Dims to ASME B36.10	2", ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP304H Dims to ASME B36.10	to be delivered until December '25
Flowmeter	3" Optisonic 4400 ultrasonic flowmeter	2" Optisonic 4400 ultrasonic flowmeter	delivered
Temperature sensors	ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP321H Dims to ASME B36.10	ASME B16.25, SS ASTM A312-TP304H Dims to ASME B36.10	delivered
Heat tracing acquisition and installation	MI cables (600V) y 0.33 Ohm/m 3340 W @ 230V, ordinary zone Cold Lead 1.5m	MI cables (600V) y 0.33 Ohm/m 3340 W @ 230V, ordinary zone Cold Lead 1.5m	failed to contract heat tracing
Insulation material and installation	Mineral wool, density 100kg/m ³ , 150mm thickness	Mineral wool, density 100kg/m ³ , 150mm thickness	to be delivered and installed after the installation of the valves

In the pictures below, some of the material already delivered on-site can be seen.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 2.4: SALTOpower RI upgrade materials already delivered: a) Flowmeter for HPS2 loop (dual path); b) Flowmeter for NEWSOL loop (single path); c) Piping material; d) Temperature sensors

Table 2.3: Foreseen calendar to the conclusion of open acquisitions, installation and commissioning

Designation of works	Dec' 25	Jan' 26	Fev '26	Mar' 26	Apr' 26	May '26	Jun' 26
Delivery of valves							
Welding works							
Procurement and installation of electrical heat tracing							
Installation of insulation							
Commissioning							

A commissioning plan is defined in accordance with Table 2.4. This commissioning intends to validate the measurements of the installed instrumentation and involves, in some cases, the validation from the supplier of the equipment/instrument. Three different stages should be

validated in order to consider the installation ready to operate. In the first stage shall be checked the mechanical and electrical integrity of the installation. After this verification, the line shall be filled with hot salts and shall be checked for potential leakages and stable reading from the instrumentation measurements. It shall also be tested for different mass flows and temperatures, and the reading from the instrumentation shall be validated. The last stage involves the registration and validation of tests done.

Table 2.4: Commissioning plan of the installed instrumentation

Commissioning plan		Resp.	Co-Resp.	Duration
Operational checklist				
Before filling				
1	Verify mechanical integrity of the hydraulic connections: piping, flanges, supports	AMEXOL	UEV	day 1
2	Confirm cleanliness of the piping system	AMEXOL	UEV	day 1
3	Confirm electrical installation and communication of the flowmeter, temp. sensors and control valve	ELTHERM/ SIEMENS	UEV	day 1
4	Confirm thermal insulation installation		UEV	day 1
5	Validate electrical heat tracing installation (resistance and insulation tests)	ELTHERM	UEV	
During filling				
1	Start up of the pump and beginning of circulation	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
2	Confirmation of no leakages	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
3	Verification of stable reading of the flowmeter	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
4	Test different flows and confirm flow control of the actuator	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
5	Verify response timing	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
6	Test opening and closing of the valve and different positions	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
7	Confirm response of the actuator	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
Registry and validation				
1	Plot of readings during tests	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
2	Note response time of the valve	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
3	Verify eventual noise or obstructions	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3
4	Validate according to supplier standard	UEV	UEV	day 2 & 3

2.3 Additional services offered at the Widening RI

Whereas the services previously provided in the Widening RI related more to solar field, molten salt media, hydraulic loop components or O&M operation strategies, the Widening RI upgrade positions the infrastructure in the supply of a testing bed for technologies and/or components using MS as a thermal source, either on charging (e.g. electrical heater) or discharging (e.g. thermochemical reactor) modes.

The RI upgrade enables the Widening RI to provide services in pursuit of the SALTOpower “beyond State-of-the Art” concept for the use of MS as a central energy hub with the potential of expanding MS use from CSP applications into multi-source / multi-throughput layouts, acting not only as a storage element but also as a sector coupling component, as illustrated in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Use of MS as an Energy Hub in SALTOpower "beyond State-of-the-Art concept"

Additional services might be provided in two different MS operation modes at the I/O plugs, classified/named from the connected (customer) component/system perspective:

- charging mode: hot MS is supplied at the I/O plug, providing the customer component/system under testing with a given mass flow and thermal capacity and cold(er) MS is returned at the I/O plug outlet to the MS loop;
- discharging mode: cold MS is supplied at the I/O plug, providing the customer component/system under testing with a given mass flow and thermal capacity and hot(ter) MS is returned at the I/O plug outlet to the MS loop;

As illustrated in Figure 2.5, different components and/or systems might then be serviced, as indicated (as an example) in Table 2.5. A summarized list of service testing conditions and parameters is provided in Table 2.6.

Table 2.5: Components/systems serviced in different MS operation modes

Component/System	Charging	Discharging
MS/... heat exchanger (HX)	X	X
Power block (HX MS/working fluid, expander, generator)	X	
Heat Pump (HX MS/working fluid, compressor, HX fluid/MS)		X
Electrical heater		X
Thermochemical reactor	X	X
Solar thermal field		X

Table 2.6: Additional services offered at the Widening RI

Service	MS loop	Electrical supply		Thermal supply		Thermal capacity	
		V	Pmax	Tmax - Tmin	Pmax - Pmin	Heating	Cooling
Charging testing (supply of hot MS, return of cold MS)	HPS2	230VAC	4.3MVA	Tmax (feed) 550°C, Tmin (return) 290°C	0.1 - 1 MW.th	5.0 MWh.th	1.8 MW.th
	NEWSOL	230VAC	4.3MVA	Tmax (feed) 500°C, Tmin (return) 190°C	10 - 100 kW.th	3.0 MWh.th	0.5 MW.th
Discharging testing (supply of cold MS, return of hot MS)	HPS2	230VAC	4.3MVA	Tmin (feed) 290°C, Tmax (return) 550°C	0.1 - 1 MW.th	5.0 MWh.th	1.8 MW.th
	NEWSOL	230VAC	4.3MVA	Tmin (feed) 190°C, Tmax (return) 500°C	10 - 100 kW.th	3.0 MWh.th	0.5 MW.th

3. DISTRIBUTED FACILITY

Aiming at the ensuing development of remote R&D activities and services in the Widening RI, besides exploiting the possibilities opened by external access and multi-site service modes with TOP partners RIs, the design, installation and commissioning of a distributed facility, encompassing the remote monitoring of different testing parameters in different assets of the RIs, ensuring data processing and backup, enforcing FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) research data management, providing proper data security (including data recovery), implemented within a Data Management Plan, was sought within the scope of SALTOpower Task 2.4.

The Distributed Facility represents the digital backbone of the consortium's integrated research infrastructure. Its conception, design, and implementation aimed to create a shared digital environment capable of interconnecting the various pilot systems operated across the participating partners — DLR, ENEA and UEvora — to enable remote monitoring, data processing, and collaborative R&D activities.

In the definition and implementation of a pilot of this distributed facility:

- a list of assets to be integrated, on the side of each RI, was defined;
- a list of sensors and a layout scheme for each asset was defined;
- a common front-end was defined;
- a framework for data management, access and storage was defined.

Implementation of the distributed facility functionalities follows a shared system architecture and common front-end, enabling the consecutive addition of additional assets along time.

3.1 System architecture definition

The distributed facility functions as the central integration layer that links different research assets and pilot units in different RIs, establishing the foundation for data collection, processing, visualization, and secure access. It was conceived to support remote access to research and innovation activities by integrating RIs and RI assets pertaining to SALTOpower JRA topics into an interoperable digital system. Although each Research Infrastructure (RI) operates independently at its respective location, all of them contribute data to a shared digital environment, ensuring interoperability, synchronization, and consistent access to experimental information.

The remote monitoring system developed within the SALTOpower project enables the acquisition, storage, and visualization of operational data generated across its experimental systems. Conceived as a distributed yet integrated platform, the architecture interconnects three different levels of information:

- pilot asset: each pilot (equipment, system, prototype, etc.) operated independently under its own local control and safety system;
- RI: the data gathered in each of the pilot assets therein included are gathered in a RI based local server;
- distributed facility: data gathered in each of the RIs local servers is linked to a central server upon a common database and front-end structure.

To achieve this, the architecture follows a structured data flow:

1. **Data collection** – Each pilot unit exports daily CSV files containing sensor measurements;
2. **Data upload** – A Python-based script reads these files and uploads the data to InfluxDB, a dedicated time-series database, stored in the local RI server;
3. **Data mapping** – A JSON configuration file defines the meaning of each variable (e.g., temperature, location, timestamp) and is stored in the respective RI local server, ensuring standardized structure;

4. **Data display** – Grafana dashboards provide a uniformized environment for the visualization of data stored, through the use of the common database management framework provided by InfluxDB, in the different RI local servers, enabling visualization of the stored data through interactive charts, tables, and gauges accessible via a web interface
5. **User access and collaboration** – Access rights are managed locally, i.e., each RI defines access to the data stored on its local server. Access rules are implemented locally, by a unique RI admin user. User access falls into two different categories, ensuring secure multi-user collaboration across institutions: editors, who might edit dashboards, and viewers, who have view-only permissions.

This architecture is scalable, modular, and FAIR-oriented, supporting the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. It is designed to evolve toward real time monitoring once stable internet connectivity is deployed across all pilot sites, enabling all participating RIs to contribute continuously to a unified digital map for collaborative research and data sharing.

Figure 3.1: System architecture definition

3.2 Data management and access

The data management and access strategy developed within the SALTOpower project ensures that all experimental information generated across the pilot systems is securely stored, systematically organized, and made available to authorized users. Building on the digital architecture described in the previous section, this framework governs how data is handled once acquired from storage and backup to access and visualization, guaranteeing transparency, traceability, and long-term availability.

The system architecture ensures both the independence and autonomy of each RI, responsible for the storage and securing of the data generated by its RIU assets, while ensuring interoperability and remote access through a common database and data visualization front-end framework.

The data storage framework is designed around a layered structure that integrates local acquisition and central management. Each RI temporarily stores data locally on acquisition systems. Once uploaded to the RI local server, all information is processed and stored in the InfluxDB time-series database, where each record is timestamped and tagged with metadata identifying its origin, loop, and variable type. Users interact with the data stored in each of the RI local servers, through the Grafana front-end, which connects directly to InfluxDB and enables both live and historical visualization.

3.2.1 User access

All users authenticate through secure login protocols (HTTPS or VPN), ensuring that data access remains traceable and consistent with institutional cybersecurity standards. In addition to general authentication and VPN protection, user management within Grafana follows a role-based configuration that defines both the scope and permissions of each account.

Within Grafana - the centralized data visualization framework, thus the external access gate for remote users - access to specific data series can be provided, asset wise:

- to a group of assets across different RIs, organized in a “project” (e.g. SALTOpower assets);
- to a group of assets within one given RI, organized in a folder (or, in alternative, in a project) (e.g. UEvora EMSP assets);
- to one single asset (e.g. UEvora EMSP-HPS2 loop).

and, access type wise, in one of three different roles:

- **Viewers** can access dashboards in read-only mode;
- **Editors** can modify or create dashboards within their project folder;
- **Admins** have extended privileges to manage users, adjust data sources, or configure settings.

This structure enables control over access and prevents cross-project data exposure. This centralized definition of asset access and user roles is implemented, upon due instructions by the RI administrator, by the Grafana administrator of the RI (i.e., each RI has one administrator, responsible for providing instructions on access and users type, and one Grafana administrator, responsible for implementing those instructions in Grafana).

3.2.2 Open Access and FAIR Data

In view of the public nature of both the RIs engaged in SALTOpower distributed facility and of the funds used in the construction of the different assets therein existing (in a general sense, though there might be exceptions), by default (i.e. if not explicitly justified and approved otherwise) all data stored in the RI local servers is PUBLIC and its management through the common database framework ensures its FAIR principles compliance.

Exceptions to this default classification might be approved, within each RI, upon request duly framed and justified, which might apply, e.g. within the framework of service contracts pertaining to confidentiality of procedures and/or results.

To this end, a specific “Data Protection Request” form has been defined and implemented in the SALTOpower website² to ensure management of experimental data across the project infrastructures. The form allows users to formally request temporary restrictions on data access related to specific assets, components, or sensors. Its main objective is to safeguard sensitive or proprietary data during defined experimental campaigns while maintaining full traceability and overall project data governance.

The form is structured to guide users through the process of defining and justifying their data protection requests. The initial section concerns the selection of the infrastructure–asset, while the following sections provide infrastructure-specific information, including visual representations and component details, as presented in the next figure.

² <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/private-data/>

a)

SALTpower Data Protection Request

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Infrastructure-Asset *

UEVORA-EMSP-HPS2 Loop

UEVORA-EMSP-NEWSOL loop

ENEA-PCS Loop

DLR-TESES Loop

Outra: _____

Seguinte
Limpar formulário

b)

Figure 3.2: Overview of the Data Protection Request Form: (a) General interface and (a) introductory section available on the SALTpower website

Each infrastructure section includes a layout drawing of the system, a list of engaged components (Figure 3.3), a Process and Instrumentation Diagram, and a list of engaged sensors (Figure 3.4). These elements ensure that the scope of the request is clearly linked to the experimental configuration and monitored parameters.

Figure 3.3: Infrastructure layout example and list of engaged components for the selected infrastructure

Figure 3.4: Example of detailed process flow and monitored sensors

Subsequent sections collect the description of the work, where users outline the objectives, experimental campaign details, and desired operational conditions, as well as the data protection description, including the justification of the request, definition of the protection period, and identification of the specific sensors or datasets to be protected, together with any exclusions, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Example of form fields for justification, period definition, and sensor selection

By combining visual system representations with structured input fields, the form ensures that all data protection requests are standardized, traceable, and well-documented, enabling consistent data management procedures and secure collaboration. Once the request is reviewed and approved, the restriction on sensor data results is applied for the specified period, in accordance with the defined justification and duration.

3.3 Current status of installation and commissioning

The installation and commissioning activities for the remote monitoring system are currently in implementation. The system has been successfully deployed on a local server at the Widening RI, hosting both InfluxDB and Grafana within Docker containers. This configuration allows continuous data collection, visualization, and testing of monitoring functionalities. The current setup is operational and is being validated with data from the experimental loops to check for stability and compatibility with the monitoring architecture described in the previous sections. The Python-based data upload routine is functional. User accounts have been configured according to defined access levels (Viewer, Editor, Admin), and preliminary dashboards have been developed to display historical variables from the EMSP systems.

Each experimental loop is equipped with sensors that monitor key operational parameters such as temperature, pressure, flow, level, and electrical resistance, essential for system control and safety. Where required, additional sensors, such as for digital NOx analysis, can be installed to enhance data resolution.

At the current stage, most pilot systems export data locally in CSV format. These data files are automatically processed by a Python-based ingestion routine, which reads and reformats them according to the corresponding JSON configuration.

```
{
  "Bottom temperature": {
    "measurement": "temperature",
    "field": "value",
    "tags": {
      "sensor": "bottom",
      "layer": "bottom",
      "tank": "hot",
      "unit": "degC",
      "mapping_version": "1.0"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 3.6: Schematic representation of the data mapping process, where the JSON file defines how parameters from CSV files are identified

The processed datasets are then uploaded to InfluxDB, where they are stored as time-series data. Once in the database, they become instantly accessible through Grafana dashboards for visualization. As network connectivity improves across all pilot sites, the architecture will evolve to support real-time data streaming. This upgrade will allow near-instantaneous synchronization between local systems and the central monitoring platform, reducing manual intervention and improving the timeliness of data analysis.

Figure 3.7: Data stored InfluxDB definition

A shared visualization platform based on Grafana provides access to monitoring data from all RIs within the SALTOpower project. Grafana acts as the digital gateway to the monitoring environment, retrieving information directly from InfluxDB and displaying it through customizable dashboards. Dashboards are organized by project and system, enabling users to explore data from individual experiments. Researchers and operators can interact with the dashboards and export visualizations for further analysis. As network infrastructure advances, Grafana will also support real-time dashboards, enhancing system supervision and collaboration among distributed partners.

Figure 3.9: Example of visualization dashboard on Grafana

The current tests of implementation at the local RI server and connection to the centralized Grafana framework through the common InfluxDB database framework are to be extended to the remaining RI local servers at DLR and ENEA.

To this end, a list of assets to be included in the SALTOpower distributed facility has already been defined for each of the engaged RIs, as presented in Table 3.1, each of which includes a layout scheme and a list of sensors, enabling due information to be included in the Data Privacy Request form described in section 3.2.

Table 3.1: Remote Monitoring RI Assets description

RI	Loop	Main Components	Engaged sensors
UEvora	EMSP-HPS2 Loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molten salt storage tanks - Molten salt drainage tank - Solar field - Steam generator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cold and hot tank thermocouples - Cold and hot salt tank level sensors - Cold and hot tank electrical resistances - NOx sensors on molten salt tanks - Thermocouples on SCA 1–4 - Flowmeter (solar field inlet) - Pressure sensor (SCA4 outlet) - Cold, hot, and drainage pumps
	EMSP-NEWSOL Loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermocline tank - Levelling tank - Cooling system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molten salt tank thermocouples - Molten salt tank level sensor - Molten salt tank electrical resistances
ENEA	PCS Loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molten salt storage tank - Solar field - Expansion tank - Air heat exchanger - Electrical heater 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermocouples in the storage tank - Level sensor in the storage tank - Thermocouples in the solar field - Flowmeter
DLR	TESIS Loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cold tank - Hot tank - Thermocline section 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cold tank thermocouples - Hot tank thermocouples - Thermocline thermocouples - Cold tank level sensor - Hot tank level sensor

Figure 3.10 shows an example of the EMSP-NEWSOL Loop. The schematic layout (a) illustrates the main system components, and the Process and Instrumentation Diagram (b) details the corresponding sensor positions and control points integrated into the monitoring system.

a)

b)

Figure 3.10: Schematic layout (a) and Process and Instrumentation Diagram (b)

At the current stage, the system operates through a Docker-based environment installed on a dedicated local computer with a fixed IP address. Within this setup, both InfluxDB and Grafana run as containers, forming an integrated environment for data storage and visualization. This configuration was adopted as an interim solution during the commissioning phase, allowing the team to test, validate, and refine the monitoring workflows before deployment on the final server.

Figure 3.11: Docker-based environment definition

A migration plan has already been defined to move the local setup to the institutional server hosted by the High Performance Computing (HPC) center of the University of Évora. The future configuration will consolidate all components within a secure and scalable infrastructure managed by the HPC Division. This transition will ensure higher data availability, improved cybersecurity, and automated backup routines.

The migration process will involve creating complete Docker backups of the InfluxDB database and Grafana dashboards, transferring these containers to the institutional server, restoring the database from the exported volumes, and reconfiguring IP settings and access permissions to

maintain continuity across the system. Once finalized, the server-based system will become the permanent data hub for the SALTOpower monitoring framework.

The next steps before full commissioning, summarized in Table 3.2, include:

- Migration to the institutional HPC server, following the backup and deployment procedure defined in Section 3.2;
- Integration of additional RIs into the monitoring framework, ensuring that each pilot site transmits data using the same format and conventions;
- Configuration of automated backup routines within the HPC environment to ensure data redundancy and recovery;
- Development of standardized dashboard templates to unify data visualization across projects;
- User training and access validation, ensuring all partners can log in and navigate their assigned workspaces;
- Final verification tests to confirm data integrity and continuous synchronization between local acquisition units and the central database.

Table 3.2: Foreseen calendar for completion of the remaining installation and commissioning activities of the SALTOpower remote monitoring system

Designation of works	Oct' 25	Nov' 25	Dec' 25	Jan' 26
Migration to the institutional HPC server				
Integration of additional RIs into the monitoring framework				
Configuration of automated backup routines within the HPC environment				
Development of standardized dashboard templates				
User training and access validation				
Final verification tests and full commissioning				

4. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artifact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artifact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Deliverables Acceptance Plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SALTOPOWER.14-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
5	Deliverables Acceptance Checklist	Project Folder
6	Technical detail and materials list for D2.2 <SALTOPOWER_M7-28052024>	Project Folder